

Music Consumption and Design: Media Formats and their Impact on Consumer Emotion

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Abstract: This article discusses the relationship between emotion and design, focusing on a specific type of experience design: musical consumption. An aspect of musical experience – media type (or consumption context) – is the object of analysis. This was carried out by means of an experimental study with students, seeking to identify differences in their perception of emotions after having been exposed to a song via different media: a sound recording (audio only), a music video and the live concert experience. The main hypothesis for this study comprised the idea that, dependent on media type, there is a significant difference in the perception of emotions. The results point to the existence of differences, suggesting the importance of socially relevant factors in the individual perception of emotions.

Keywords: *Design, emotion, experience, music, media.*

1. Introduction

The relevance of the role performed by emotions in the process of consumption retains vast recognition within the theoretical field. This emotional component is emphasized from both a cognitive [1, 3] and a social [4,5] perspective.

On this basis, the importance of emotions has gained noteworthiness for the study of design, as the former becomes a fundamental element in the construction of memorable experiences for the consumer, and is related to the desirable effects associated with the consumer decision process, such as recommendation and repurchase, according to Norman [7], Hawkins, Mothersbaugh and Best [8], Holbrook and Hirschman [9] e Firat and Dholakia [10]. This is why knowledge of the emotional component becomes fundamental to the design of goods and services.

Musical contexts become particularly interesting for the study of emotions: first, because a certain consensus exists regarding the capability of music to produce emotions in its listeners, independent of the situation in which this music is experienced [11]; additionally, the musical experience can be understood as a consumption experience – it can be investigated through an expansive base of conceptual theory [12, 13, 14, 15].

Setting out from the observation that musical consumption occurs through an ample variety of digital and physical platforms and, taking into account constant technological and cultural innovation, this article proposes an investigation of the effect of emotions on the consumption of music: the relation between the type of media used and the type and intensity of the emotions perceived by the consumer. Thus, the principal question within this study can be synthesized as: how does the consumer perceive the importance of a live musical presentation as part of the consumption process, and how does this importance manifest emotionally?

For this reason, experimental research was carried out with undergraduate students with ages ranging between 18 and 24, with the purpose of analyzing the type and intensity of emotion generated by the consumption of music within the context of three presentation modes: via a sound recording, as an audiovisual clip and through the projected mental experience of a live concert.

The results show that there is a substantial difference between emotions perceived in distinct contexts through different media and that these differences can be linked to social and identity-building factors. Some directions for subsequent research are presented as final considerations.

2. Consumption and Emotion

Literature about emotions involved in the consumption and purchase process takes a cognitive approach, where psychology constitutes the footing for discussion and research [16]. Blackwell, Miniard and Engel [17, p. 81] cite emotional interference as an intervening variable during the Consumer Decision Process, noting that “emotional trade-off difficulty effects on choice are obtained even after controlling for effects that are attributable to subjects' relative importance weights for the quality versus currency attributes ” [27].

A similar approach is proposed by Chitturi, Raghunathan and Mahajan [3] and Oliver [1,2], who transpose the study of emotion present in marketing to the area of design. The authors observe how the attributes of design objects are involved in the generation of emotions for the consumer, as well as the stimulus of response behavior (re-purchase and recommendation). Even though this illustrates a positive stance regarding the emotional phenomenon, the underlying approach is strictly cognitive, presupposing that nature of emotion is an individual phenomenon, partially explainable and controllable through the stimulus-response model.

By addressing the social aspect of emotion, Ayrosa *et al.* [17] highlight another line of thought which offers a revision of cognitive and constructivist literature on the subject. They expound on a vision with substantial underpinnings in psychology that came to enjoy a certain consensus regarding the affirmation that emotions are

socially constructed. According to these authors, emotions are a product of the junction of a general stimulus and specific socio-cultural factors.

This affirmation should be interpreted in a consumer society context, in accordance with the descriptions of McCracken [19], where the consumer is someone engaged in a cultural project, where the objective is to complete the self. In this way, emotions can also be part of a broader process of symbolic construction, while linked to the experiences of a consumption system that supplies individuals with the raw materials for the realization of their respective “varied and mutant ideas about what it is to be a man or a woman, a middle aged or elderly person, a father, citizen and a professional” [19, p.119]. Accordingly, a relation can be established between emotions and the construction of identity, by means of a shared consumption experience, which has a complex nature of interconnected aesthetic, cognitive and symbolic aspects.

Maffesoli [4] states that, in addition to the identity-construction approach, the aesthetic approach also makes viable an understanding of feelings and of shared experience in mass consumption contexts. There would be, in situations of collective consumption, a Dionysiac trend, in Maffesoli's words where the individual would be able to be "removed from himself" through a moment of ecstasy, provided by the mechanism of emotion, collectively shared. This trend can be seen in the search for tactile relations, such as "unicity", through mass demonstrations of social consumption, such as concerts and sporting events or tours, be it through a search for the epiphany of a "we" in virtual communities, rave parties, spending time together at malls and other places where a situation of "being together for no special reason" can be created.

Thus, one can see how the emotional consumption phenomenon allows for different readings, from a circumscribed and individual event to something socially constructed and characterized by a strong aesthetic and cultural component. In this second approach, one can underscore, first, the symbolic constructivist component, where emotion can be linked to objects and situations that contribute to the construction of the self; second, the aesthetic component, where emotion has value as a link between individuals in specific situations of consumption, as in, for example, concerts.

3. Emotion and Design

For Norman (7), there are several levels of the cognitive and emotional system that go into operation the moment that an object becomes the target of an individual's attention. The first is the visceral level, also called pre-conscious, since it precedes thought, where first impressions are formed. This is said of the product's initial impact, the feeling it causes. The second level, behavioral, is attributed to the experience with the product. The third level, reflective, is where conscience is found and the highest levels of feeling, emotions and cognition, are experienced.

It is also possible to observe another difference in the levels, according to Norman. Norman argues that time is another distinctive factor because the visceral and behavioral levels become connected that moment the

consumption experience is happening, while the reflective level extends for a much greater period of time. This shows that the reflective level establishes a long-term relationship with the feeling of satisfaction produced while the experience of consuming the product is happening.

In this sense it is possible to trace a parallel the explanation given by Mothersbaugh and Best (8) with respect to emotions relating to products and brands. For these theorists, emotions are strong feelings, in a certain way uncontrollable, that affect people's behavior. While undergoing physiological changes, such as increase in cardiac rhythm, individuals are showing emotions brought about by atmospheric events or mental processes. They are specific changes resulting from the situation experienced.

According to Norman, there is the concept of self, which is very closely connected to the brain's reflective level and dependent on cultural norms. They are aspects that express the public appearance that individuals have of themselves, such as the way they dress and behave, and the material things that own. The desire to be seen favorably by others is universal, whether in more individualistic western societies, or in eastern societies with emphasis on the group.

Thus, we can see that the advertising industry makes use of this characteristic relating to the high level of importance given by individual to other people's opinions. The strategy becomes the association of products with happy, satisfied people, doing things that suggest the fantasy of a future buyer, such as a vacation in a paradisiacal, exotic place, meals in other countries, and so on. Famous people or those who have an influence on consumers induce these associations, generating a feeling of worth (7,p.75). That which is bought or the lifestyle adopted by an individual reflects and determines his or her self-image and the image seen by others. Thus, advertisements acquire material that stimulates emotions with the goal of increasing attention, level of processing, remembrance and preference of the brand by the individual.

For Norman (7), there is a certain roll for products and services that have entertainment and style as a goal, where enormous individual differences, for people and cultures, become important. It is in this category that design is dictated by people and by market segment. In this sense, it is possible to state that experience has a fundamental role in the consumer's decision to buy. According to Holbrook and Hirschman (9), experience is an individual happening, with a significant emotional importance and based on the interaction of a stimulus, represented by the products and services consumed.

In this way, music's role becomes fundamental in the projection of experience, once the individual's emotional side is evoked through stimulus, with reference to the cultural and social framework. Besides music, other multi-sensorial, imaginary, and emotive aspects have been awakened through the design of experience. In sequence, the approach will be given with the perspective of music and its consumption.

4. Music and Musical Consumption

The study of emotions in relation to music consumption has increased recently through initiatives and academic entities aligned toward this focal point. The area of Sonic Interaction Design (SID) shows a particularly relevant approach, because it is based, in part, on traditional design to develop theories about the projection and reception of sound.

Reactions dedicated by individuals in relation to sound perception have been dealt with in a recent report by Closing the Loop of Sound Evaluation and Design -- CLOSED. The study points out sound's interpretive role in relation to different reception contexts and the influence of sound in the interpretation of visual objects.

For Norman (7), the influence that music has on the subject's dedicated states is universal, and these states are similar in different cultures. Norman states that music's structural outlines in different cultures are also similar citing analogous factors on an acoustic, psychoacoustic and interpretive order regarding the reception of sound.

According to Norman (7), music affects the listener on all levels of emotional processing -- visceral, behavioral and reflective. The listener is affected directly on a visceral level by acoustic, musical stimuli. This happens when the subject is directed toward carrying out a hearing activity, as when music reaches him in a subconscious way. The behavioral appeal for the subject is related to understanding and consciously anticipating the structure of the musical work. There is a strong relationship to the creation of expectations, which can be satisfied or violated in relation to the rhythmic and harmonic development of the music. Finally, the reflective dimension of music reception is related to the effects of "delight, surprise or shock" which music can cause (7, p.116).

The importance of the sound product -- the recording itself -- also contributes as an emotional stimulus. Young people put great emotional value on the objects produced by their favorite artists, as well as their recordings (20). Thus, they establish an emotional relationship through the songs with which they identify. In the same way, young people have developed a behavior of sharing the music consumption experience. In this behavior, there is a component of participation in collective musical experiences with other enthusiasts.

Levitan (13) explains the form through which composers mold the formal characteristics of music to convey various emotions that make up human experience (13). "Our ability to make sense of music depends on experience", Levitan states (13, p.106). This suggests an individual's own musical grammar whose close association with his culture makes it possible to arrive at meaning, and the practices of musical artists that "imbue the music with emotion" (13, p.109).

This perspective opens the possibility of reflecting on others who have influenced the process of reception, which is not emission. Marshall McLuhan (14) approaches the significance of the means of the communicative process. In musical grammar, which starts with musical composition, the means also supplies meaning over the nature of the reception experience. In fact, according to the definition which establishes one medium as the

content of another medium or other media (14, p.8), the musical composition itself is a mediation between the music and the receptor. In the same way, reproduction technology gives meaning to the activity of the listener's interpretation.

It is this technological mediation that is to be studied, because it is here that music can achieve new meaning: if mediation changes the experience of music consumption, what could the resulting emotional repercussions be?

David, Horton and German (15) studied the role performed by affection in the reception of a sporting event. They explain that the key factor in affectionate reactions in mediated contexts is empathy, or disposition in relation to the object mediated. This empathy is equally present, according to David et al, in the in-person and televised reception of sports -- spectators show a level of involvement that is instinctive and beyond their will. Music concerts can also be seen in an in-person form and/or mediated through video. In the next section, we try to understand the emotional dynamic of the relationship with the musical object.

5. The Experiment: Methodological Procedures

Based on what has been presented, an experiment was developed, aiming at contributing to the understanding of how media, or the form of consumption, influences the emotions involved in music consumption. This research was used on three groups of students between 18 and 24 years old, from the undergraduate courses Rock Producers and Musicians, Audiovisual Production and Management for Innovation and Leadership, from a private Brazilian university, from November to December 2009. The criterion for the selection of the groups was accessibility, the only restriction being the age group. This is because, according to Kusek and Gerd (21), the generation born between 1976 and 1998 makes up the most relevant demographic for the study of digital music consumption, as they are educated in the use of new media and motivated to interact with virtual environments. This position is corroborated by the International Federation of the Phonographic Industry (25), which cites the relevance of young people between 16-29 years old, such as students, with regard to music consumption.

The experiment lasted 20 minutes, during which three different musical consumption experiences for the same music recording were simulated. These were: listening to the recording (situation 1); listening to the recording along with images (video - situation 2); and, participating in a music concert (this situation was reproduced by means of reading a fictitious/staged situation - situation 3). The groups were exposed for about 2 minutes and 30 seconds to the recording in each of the stages of the experiment. They were given questionnaires with scales to register emotions perceived after each experience. At the end, questions were asked related to socio-cultural variables and consumption habits (type of media used, places and times of consumption, individual or collective consumption, etc.) The recording selected for use in this research, the song Back in Black, by the band AC/DC, was selected through observation of the groups with which the research was done.

The hypotheses of this study, to be verified by means of the experiment, were as follows:

H1: There is an influence by the media/form of consumption over emotions perceived during the process of musical consumption. This hypothesis, in order to be verified, required a high level of variation among the answers, in the three diverse situations.

H2: The intensity of emotions is greater in the case of the form of the presentation that involves situations of co-presence (concerts) or looking at pictures (video).

Besides verifying these hypotheses, the study proposed to investigate the possible existence of relationships of the emotions perceived and the consumption habits of the participants. In this way, we tried to amplify the understanding of the relationship of emotions and the role of the situation of musical consumption, verifying the relationship of the use of video-sharing software and the individual/collective dimension of consumption. These considerations, which are described in the conclusions of the study obviously do not have definite value, but suggest relationships and possible clues for future researchers.

Students from three undergraduate courses – Leadership and Innovation Management and Audiovisual Production –reacted positively immediately upon being told they would hear an audio reproduction, even before the music began to be played. During the first chords of Back in Black, the song by Australian rock band AC/DC, we observed students expressing non-verbal approval and familiarity with the music. Very few exhibited indifference. Some individuals lip-synched to the lyrics, as well as moving their feet, hands and/or head to the rhythm. This behavior was prominent during the following phases as well, when students watched video and audio simultaneously, and later when they were told to imagine a live concert environment.

Students from the Rock Production and Musicianship undergraduate course, bringing added experience to their more technical approach to music, were perceived to be more attentive throughout the research process. The individuals from this course were focused during the entire experiment, and the group seized opportunities to address doubts about the research questions.

6. Data Analysis

The collected data were tabulated and analyzed with the help of SPSS Statistics Data Editor v.17 software. Observations undertaken were the frequency analysis, comparison of averages and matching analysis in order to identify the significant differences between the averages of the perception of emotions in the three stages of the research (music consumption by means of audio, video or concert).

The range of emotions investigated was developed from a model by Watson et al. (22) which works with a set of positive and negative emotions, evaluated according to the level of intensity of the occurrence of each emotion. The chosen set of twelve emotions was adapted, worked out in a way to guarantee a balance between positive and negative feelings, with there being six emotions at each pole (see Table 1). The emotions were distributed in a random manner on the questionnaire sheet and were measured on a scale of “none” (score of 1) to “a great deal” (score of 5).

One first consideration regarding the fundamental hypothesis as to this work, is whether there is an influence by the media/form of consumption over the emotions perceived during the process of musical consumption. In order to verify this hypothesis, the average scores of each type of emotion (emotion-x) were submitted to a matching analysis, aimed at detecting the presence of significant differences between pairs of variables among the three types of musical consumption formats (phonogram, video, and concert), in the following order: emotion-x situation 1 vs. emotion-x situation 2; emotion-x situation 2 vs. emotion-x situation 3; emotion-x situation 3 vs. emotion-x situation 1.

It was possible to observe significant differences for the most intense emotions experienced on the average in the three situations, in order of relevance: intense interest, joy, fascination and enchantment. The ranking of the emotions shown in Table 1 is oriented for the reading of these data.

Table 1. Scores for Emotion Intensity

Type of Emotion	Average Score	Type of Emotion	Average Score
Intense Interest	4.15	Tranquility	1.72
Joy	3.66	Irritation	1.57
Inspiration	3.23	Repulsion	1.46
Fascination	3.06	Aversion	1.44
Enchantment	3.03	Sadness	1.17
Agitation	2.02	Disinterest	1.13

The test of the matching analysis (Table 2) indicated significant differences in the comparison of the pairs situation 1 - situation 3 (audio and concert) and situation 2 - situation 3 (video and concert) for the emotions “enchantment” and “joy”. As far as the emotion identified as “extreme interest”, the test showed partially significant differences in the comparison of video vs. concert, but not in the comparison of concert vs. video. Nevertheless, in contrast to H2, the data show the intensity of the emotion was greater in the consumption using audio (4.34 = audio / 3.83 = video). In all of the other cases, emotion experienced in the concert situation was more intense than the other two consumption situations.

Different interpretations can be given. One to be taken into consideration has to do with the form of presentation of the stimulus, which was sequential (audio - video - concert) and could have influenced the answer. The surprise factor could be one of the key elements that contributed to raising the attention level and the feeling of emotions, according to Oliver’s disconfirmation paradigm (1). Annotations in this regard are presented in the final considerations of this article. Nevertheless, the observed data show that the intensity of emotions experienced through exposure to sound stimulus would be greater in the case of visual stimulus, which would reject H2.

Table 2. Matching Analysis of Emotions by Type of Consumption Situation

	Differences among variables		
	Average	Standard Variation	Significance
Intense Interest			
Situation 1 vs. Situation 2	.508	1.040	.000
Situation 2 vs. Situation 3	-.483	1.080	.001
Situation 3 vs. Situation 1	-.034	1.008	.795
Joy			
Situation 1 vs. Situation 2	.169	.931	.167
Situation 2 vs. Situation 3	-.897	1.280	.000
Situation 3 vs. Situation 1	.741	1.358	.000
Fascination			
Situation 1 vs. Situation 2	.052	.999	.695
Situation 2 vs. Situation 3	-1.035	1.195	.000
Situation 3 vs. Situation 1	.966	1.363	.000
Enchantment			
Situation 1 vs. Situation 2	-.034	.946	.784
Situation 2 vs. Situation 3	-1.034	1.025	.000
Situation 3 vs. Situation 1	1.052	1.234	.000

Thereafter, the sample was divided into two groups, based on gender (men = 55.9 %; women = 44.1 %). Some significant observations resulted from a comparison of the emotion perception averages between the two groups. The averages shown by the group of women were higher in most cases, for consumption via audio (9 emotions in the 12 investigated), video (10 in 12) and concert (7 in 12). An analysis related to the sign of emotion shows that there is a difference in the three consumption situations: women show higher averages for all the positive valence emotions (intense interest, joy, inspiration, fascination, enchantment). Another confirmation comes from the negative valence emotions (agitation, irritation, aversion, repulsion, sadness, disinterest), which were experienced with higher intensity by the women in the case of the musical via concert experience (6 of 6).

This observation seems to be supported in the repetition of the same matching analysis test for the two groups, where it was possible to observe the case of the most intense emotion perceived via video and via concert was clearly more significant in the men's group, while in the women's group the test gave a negative result. Some interpretations may be proposed with respect to this, taking into consideration the type of music and the musical

preferences, discussed in the final considerations section below. In any event, we consider it advisable to note these matters and suggest that they be developed in future analysis.

7. Conclusions

Before proposing any type of interpretation of the data presented above, some limitations of the study should be taken into consideration. As to the method of conducting the experiment, where the groups were submitted to three stimuli in sequence (audio, video, concert), it should be pointed out that the order of presentation may have been a possible influence. This observation is induced by the observation of the behavior of the most representative emotional variable, according to the answers, "Intense interest".

The intensity of this emotion was greatest in the consumption situation via audio, while all the other emotions that show significant differences point to the concert situation as the situation generating the most intense emotions (enchantment, fascination and joy). One possible way to overcome this limitation would be to conduct the experiment with control groups, showing different stimuli to each group.

Another limitation in the experiment was the type of music presented and its relation to the consumers' tastes and preferences. For the analysis of preferences of type of music, it was seen that the majority of the participants mentioned rock as their favorite type of music, there being observed a clear predominance of positive emotions. This limitation may be overcome through a repetition of the experiment with a more heterogeneous public and the diversification of the musical stimuli to be presented, which it is hoped will be done in the future.

The fact that the participants stated the intensity of their emotions, given that it was not possible by the nature of the experiment and the resources available to use any other method of measuring, can also be seen as a limitation, considering that in this way the object of the study comprised solely the reflexive perceptions of the subjects as to their own emotions, and not the visceral manifestations. This limitation may be overcome through the application of other control methods, for example, cardiac rhythm or neuroscience studies, such as those developed by Lindstrom (26) through the use of magnetic resonance exams. Nevertheless, it is thought that the study of the reflexive emotion component is of particular interest for the understanding of the processes of interpretation of the experience for the construction of the self, such as seen mainly in the case of the differences by gender.

In conclusion, in spite of the limitations of the study, some interesting annotations may be synthesized in relation to the verification of the research hypotheses. With relation to H1, significant differences were observed in the emotions perceived during the musical consumption, especially in the comparison between concert and audio and concert and video. In other words, it was possible to observe that the consumption situation of the musical event, which involved a series of visual, audio and tactile stimuli and bears the esthetic aspect of "being

together”, as described by Maffesoli (4), was clearly different from the others, shown in the mainly positive emotions experienced by the participants.

As for the musical consumption accompanied by video images, the intensity perceived in the emotions did not show significant differences in relation to consumption via phonogram, no confirming H2. However, the limitations of the study described above should be taken into account.

The observation of the differences between the genders suggests a series of other considerations, related to the social nature of emotions, in line with the position of the symbolic interactionists presented by Ayrosa et al. (16) and with the concept of self in Norman (7). The fact that positive emotions were perceived with greater intensity among men, and the negative emotions were much stronger among women, solely in the case of consumption via concert, contrasting the tendency of greater emotional intensity among women (independent of the sign) observable in the other two situations, could lead to sociologic considerations about the social construction of the “rock concert” product and its relevance in the construction of self project of young men and women, in the observed context. If these observations are confirmed by further analysis, it could suggest that the intensity of the perceived emotion would depend, partially, on the meanings produced and attributed socially to a determined consumption product/situation and its significance and relevance to the individual, in relation to his or her perception of self and of the reference groups. These considerations have a clear impact on design of musical experiences, inasmuch as they point to the importance of the social context and the reference group as impacting factors on the intensity of experienced emotions.

Unfortunately, these suggestions must remain as hypotheses for now. Possible paths to widen these results could arise by performing experiments with distinct types of music or the more accurate simulation of the experience context of a concert or live presentation. It is believed that this makes up a field of analysis to be explored through future research, in an effort to understand the working of the social component on the perception of emotions in the dynamics of identity construction.

8. References

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